

ISic1228

I.Sicily inscription 1228

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

volcanic

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140714

1. Αίλιω Ἀδριανῶ
2. Ἀντωνείνωι
3. Σεβαστῶ Εὐσεβεῖ
4. π (ατρὶ) π (ατρίδος) .
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492834

EDCS 39101594

PHI 140714

Bibliography

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